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Methods for Determining Soil Contamination by Oil and Petroleum Products and Indicator Plants in the North of Caspian Sea

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Received Date: 07-July-2020

Accepted Date: 29-July-2020

Published Date: 31-Aug-2020

Abstract.

In accordance with the Law "On environmental protection "and " the plan of comprehensive measures to improve the environmental situation in the Republic of Azerbaijan (for 2006-2010)", as well as a program on the scientific topic, revealed methods for studying soil contamination with oil and petroleum products on the Northern coast of the Caspian Sea and on the basis of this were studied plants-indicators.

Since the second half of the XX century, anthropogenic factors and technogenic impacts on the environment have been increasing in our country, as well as in the area of oil fields, oil products, mineralized water, etc. negatively affect vegetation in the zone of oil production, as well as due to waste pollution, soil fertility is degraded, and vegetation is subjected to digression.

Key words: formation, association, dominant, subdominant, indicator

Geo-botanical indication studies to study indicator plants in soils polluted with oil and oil products and conduct scientific and research works in the territory were carried out at three phases (preparatory, field, and cameral). It is recommended to determine the followings on the selected exemplary "facilities":

1. Systematization of polluted fields from the impact of the bore and mineralized lay waters on the ecological classification;
2. Classification of the degree of soil pollution with oil and oil products (according to the indicator plants);
3. Determination of fullness and usefulness scale of indicator plants at the level of formation and association, as well as, specifying indicators;
4. Scheme and mapping of geobotanical indication.

1. Research methods.

Soil cuts are taken from the area where indicator plants are spread, clean and polluted (black oil, bitumen) herbariums are collected and herbarium album is prepared.

It is appropriate to have a mobile ecological laboratory for field studies.

Relevant studies are implemented on the basis of topographic maps. The indication method is used in order to detect indicator plants while conducting phytosociological studies of soils polluted with oil and oil products by route method between oil wells (Acad. V.J.Hajiyev T.E.Gasimova, Baku, Elm, 2008.) [1,3,5,8] [10,11].

Characteristics of indicator plants are taken into account for the determination of the type, composition, and humidity of soil through plants. Therefore, indication studies of indicator plants are studied by the following studies:

- hydroindication (an indication of groundwater);
- halt indication (an indication of salinization);
- geoidication (an indication of mountain sediments and soil);
- geological excavation indication.

2. Research object and methods for the prevention of soil pollution.

The development of methods for the investigation of the degree of pollution in the soils contaminated or covered with oil and oil products referring to minerals extracted from the earth's surface and indicator plants is set forth in the modern period (Bykov B.A. Alma-Ata.1998, Viktorov, S.B., Vostokov,. 1961).

Regarding this, ecological and geobotanical studies were conducted by us in oil fields No. 1, 2, and 3 of “Siyazan oil” at the northern shore of the Caspian Sea (Samur-Shabran lowland) (in 2012-2016) (Gurbanov E.M., Huseynova Kh.Z. Natural sciences. N.Ch.Vestnik 2011. pp. 78 – 84)[12].

The investigation shows that oil and oily wastes, including mineralized layer waters, chemical reagents of good rocks are contaminated at different degrees [9, 15]. Various relief (from 2 meters to 200 meters above the sea level), gray-brown soil (gray – grass, saline), and indicator plants in ecological conditions are found in the contaminated soils of the territory. Determination of indicator plants is of great importance in the implementation of recultivation measures for the soil fertility and restoration of vegetation cover (Akhundova A.A.. Baku, 2012, Mammadov G.Sh.. Baku “Elm”, 2004, 380 p.,)[2, 7, 9, 13, 15].

3. Analysis and character of research method

Classification of the degree of soil pollution at “Siyazan oil” with oil and oil products, well and mineralized waters on the ecological impacts of residual substances[8,12,14] is compiled (table 1).

Table 1 - Ecological classification of polluted soil – vegetation cover from the impact of the well and mineralized layer waters

Degree of contamination	Sources of degradation	Residual substances	Ecological impacts	The appearance of the surface (aspect)
1	2	3	4	5
Weak	Washed in the drilling fluid	Bituminous substances 1p.c.	Projective (project) coating, up to 70 p.c. (covering with natural plants)	-
Medium	Washed liquids, gas condensate	Bituminous substances, 2.5 p.c.	Grouping of cultivated plants (participation of the indicator in saline soils)	Whitish-brown spots
Severe	Washed fluids, oil	Sulphate-salinity (dry residue - <1 p.c.), bituminous substances <3,7 p.c.	Partial reduction of vegetation	Presence of oil spots
Very severe	Discharge of highly mineralized water to the surface in emergency situations	Sulphate-chloride salt residue, - >1 p.c., bituminous substances - >5 p.c.	Complete loss of vegetation	Compaction of the soil with oil and mineralized water

Classification according to the degree of soil contamination, which are affected by plants-indicators contaminated with oil and petroleum products by the method of indigation [7, 9, 12], and their characteristics are given below (table 2).

Table 2-Classification of soils according to the degree of pollution with oil and oil products

Level of pollution	Indicator of the degree of pollution (p.c.)	Nature of distribution with plants
1	2	3
Very weak	<5	Natural herbaceous vegetation (vegetation cover) differs little in its composition and structure from polluted areas.
Weak	5-10	Thinness in the form of spots is found in natural vegetation cover.
Weak	5 – 10	It is rare in the form of spots in the state of natural grass.
Above the weak	10-15	In the state of natural covering of the grass, reduction occurs, it is rare, without covered spots.
Average	15-25	The process of plant restoration was weak; uncoated spots are very rare, the species composition of vegetation is low and has a low height.
High	25-35	Restoration of natural plants is not observed, there are isolated native species, degradation

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Level of pollution	Indicator of the degree of pollution (p.c.)	Nature of distribution with plants
1	2	3
		in the oil and bitumen coating.
Very high	35-45	They are devoid of natural vegetation cover; there are individual plants whose roots go deep into the ground, and the oil and bitumen coating is very poorly subject to degradation.
The highest	>45	It is rare to find a natural vegetation cover, the top layer of the soil is completely covered with fuel oil and bitumen, and is subject to degradation.

According to the classification given in table 2, information on the character of soils polluted with oil and indicator plants is obtained and the indication property of plant cover is determined. Therefore, investigating the relation of indicator plant found in “Siyazan oil” fields with local ecological conditions, it is suggested to identify fullness of indicators, the scale of usefulness, and their specification as follows (table 3, 4, 5). As well, based on the results of the study on the geobotanical indication, a large scale (1:50000-1:10000) “indication map” is compiled. Regarding this, the scales of fullness and usefulness are prepared according to B.A.Bikova [10], A.A.Viktorov, B.A.Vostokov, and D.A.Vishivkin [11] as a table (table 3, 4). “Exemplary points” are selected at 3 – 5 places in the clean land areas and those polluted with oil products at the research facilities (among operated oil wells). As with ecological – geobotanical studies, species composition of phylogenesis, its structure or composition (abundance, stages), and phenological phases in those areas are noted. Plant types, formation, and associations (relief, soil, humidification, etc. together with ecological factors) referring to phytosociological classification are identified [3,8, 14].

Samples with soil cuts (up to groundwater) and rocks are taken by giving the classification of “exemplary” areas in every association and herbariums of indicator plants must be collected. Ecological and chemical analysis of these samples are conducted at the laboratory.

So, the indicators of geobotanical indication are given in a special table referring to the granulometric composition of the soil, as well as, the accuracy of indicator plants (at the level of association).

Table 3-Scale referring to the fullness of the indicators of the association *Phragmiteta australis* (Cav.) with *Trin.ex Steud.* indicator

Total number (p.c.)		Indicators of accuracy	Degrees of accuracy
Number of indication objects	Number of objects without relation with indication		
100	0	∞	The highest (special indicator)
More than 90	Less than 10	10	High (full indicator)
From 70 to 90	From 10 to 25	From 3 to 10	Average (satisfactory) indicator
From 60 to 75	From 25 to 40	From 1,5 to 3	Above the weak (suspicious indicator)
Less than 60	Less than 40	1,5	Weak (impossible indicator)

In this case, the accuracy of indication of indicator plants at “exemplary” fields is determined by the following method taking into consideration soil, geological, and hydrogeological indicators by special geobotanical – indication method.

Let’s suppose that the root of *Phragmites australis* which is considered to be the dominant plant of the formation of mesophytes and hydrophyte, as well as, water-marsh plants (*Phragmiteta*) grows at the depth of 1.5 – 2 meter as the indicator of groundwater and for this purpose, areas up to the depth of 2 meters were dug (manually) at 100 exemplary fields, water was found in 95 fields out of 100, but the water was not taken from 5 fields. So, taking into account that cane which is an indicator of the water indication is at the depth up to 2 meters; $95:100=95$ or 95 p.c. is obtained. In this case, as can be seen from table 3, the degrees of accuracy consists of plants referring to the highest, high, medium, low and weak indication.

It should be added that the draft cover of cane varies between 55 – 60 p.c.; in addition, 5% *Iris pseudocorus* L. is spread sparse, *Juncus acutus* L. medium and *Iris pseudocorus* L. weakly among the species composition of the association of *Phragmites australis*, and also, it is of less importance as an indicator type.

It is recommended to note the scale of the usefulness of indicator in the association of *Juncustum acutus*-*Typhaosum Angustifolia* formed at the grassy- swampy land around Andahar village (pool covered

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with black oil) near the oil well no. 455 at the field no. 1 in the territory of the studied “Siyazan oil” field as mentioned in table 4.

Table 4-The scale of usefulness of indicator of the association of Juncusetum acutus-Typhasum angustifolia) (*Juncus acutus* C.A.Mey., *Typha angustifolia* L.)

Presence of the plant at an indication object (number in total area, p.c.)	Usefulness	
	Points	Grade
From 90 to 100	1	Excellent
From 75 to 90	2	Good
From 50 to 75	3	Normal
From 10 to 50	4	Satisfactory
From 1 to 10	5	Very satisfactory

While field studies are carried out at “exemplary” fields (scientific – research, project and survey works are intended), the indication of fields are verified, and also specified by the “selective” method on the route in the territory of oil fields after the investigations are completed at the place appropriate for geobotanical indication mentioned above. As well, practically, it is advisable to give the assessment of the accuracy of indicator - ∞ (to infinity) and its usefulness as mentioned in table 5.

Table 5-Specification of indication and usefulness of the formation of Juncusetum-typhaosum

Degrees of accuracy	Indicators of accuracy in the assessment of usefulness				
	Excellent	Good	Normal	Insignificant	Very insignificant
Special indicator	∞	∞	∞	∞	∞
Full indicator	>10	>10	>10	>10	>10
Good indicator	3-10	3-10	3-10	3-10	3-10
Suspicious indicator	1,5-3	1,5-3	1,5-3	1,5-3	1,5-3

As mentioned in the table, relevant indicators for this or that formations are determined, as well as, the composition of indicator types around oil wells is noted with “+” and “-“ if similar and with “-“ if suspicious.

4. Relation of indicator plants with soil

Based on this, the relation of the compliance of indicator types [1] in the lands where they are spread [1] (table 6). It is seen from the relation of indicator plants mentioned in the table with the soils where they are spread that the formation of saline soils in oil wells, finding *Halocnemum strobilaceous* (Pall.) Bieb.), *Petrosimonia brachiata* (Pall.) Bunge.) etc. shows the pollution of soils with oil products [10, 12].

The relevant scheme is considered to be the main criterion for the compilation of an “indication map”.

Table 6-Schemes of the relation of indicator plant species spread in the soils contaminated with oil and oil products

№	Species	Relation with soils
1.	<i>Phragmites australis</i> (Cav.) Trin ex Steud	Grassy-swampy (contaminated with black oil and layer waters)
2.	<i>(Salicornia europaea</i> L.	Saline gray-meadow and saline (contaminated with black oil)
3.	<i>Salsola dendroides</i> Pall.	Weak saline gray-meadow (contaminated with black oil)
4.	<i>Alhagi pseudoalhagi</i> (Bieb.) Desv.)	Saline gray - meadow (contaminated with black oil)
5.	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers)	Weak saline gray-meadow (contaminated with black oil)
6.	<i>Eremopyrum triticeum</i> (Gaertn.) Nevski))	Saline gray-meadow and saline (contaminated with black oil)
7.	<i>Petrosimonia brachiata</i> (Pall.) Bunge)	Saline, severely saline gray-meadow (contaminated with black oil and bitumen)
8.	<i>Tamarix ramosissima</i> Lebed.	Humid gray-meadow, saline grass-gray, swampy meadow (contaminated with black oil)
9.	<i>Typha angustifolia</i> L.	Grassy-wet and wet saline (contaminated with black oil)
10.	<i>Plantago arenaria</i> Waldst. et Kit.	Saline clay gray-grass and sandy (contaminated with black oil and bitumen)
11.	<i>Artemisia lerchiana</i> Web.	Weak saline gray-meadow and gray – brown (contaminated with black oil)
12.	<i>Juncus acutus</i> C.A.Mey	Grass – damp and weak saline gray – grass (contaminated

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No	Species	Relation with soils
		with black oil)
13.	<i>Limonium meyeri</i> (Boiss.) O. Kuntze.)	Saline gray – brown and saline clay gray – grass (contaminated with black oil)
14.	<i>Artemisia szowitziana</i> (Bess.) Grossh.	Humid saline, damp gray – grass (contaminated with black oil)
15.	<i>Nitraria schoberi</i> L.	Saline clay gray – grass (contaminated with black oil)
16.	<i>Aeluropus litteralis</i> (Gouan.) Pers.	Humid, saline, gray – grass and saline (contaminated with bitumen)
17.	<i>Halosulmum strofiloecum</i> (Pall.) Bieb.	Saline and clay, severely saline gray – grass (contaminated with black oil and bitumen)
18.	<i>Capparis herbacea</i> Willd.	Weakly saline gray – grass and clay gray – brown (contaminated with black oil)
19.	<i>Gomanthus pilosus</i> (Pall.) Bunge.	Humid, saline clay gray – grass (contaminated with bitumen)
20.	<i>Elytrigia elongatiformis</i> (Drob.) Nevski.	Saline, gray – grass and gray – brown (contaminated with black oil)

5. Research results

Based on the above mentioned, a map with the same name was made referring to the indication of soils polluted with oil products and layer waters. For this, first of all, according to the classification for the legend or the content of the plants of soils polluted with phytosociological principles and phytoindicators, ecological and geobotanical map was compiled the following works were done:

1. Physical and chemical properties of soil (granulometric composition, salinization, etc.);
2. Impact of different processes on the areas (natural and anthropogenic factors);
3. Compiling hydroindication map;
4. Compiling the map on the agricultural perspective or development (in the area);
5. Compiling ecological – geobotanical map.

According to the legend of ecological – geobotanical map compiled, ecological factors, conditional signs of dominant (indicator) plants, and colors of ecological types are mentioned in its contour.

It should be additionally noted that it is possible to compile an “indication map” with aerospace methods. At the same time, the aspects of vegetation cover or its appearance, geobotanical structure, and contamination of indicator plants with oil products are determined by the decoding method. Phytoindication map is made at different zones (in fully humid and arid zones) by this method.

Generally, using the methods on the determination of indicator plants of soils polluted with oil and oil products, the results of geobotanical indication studies can be used in the compilation of map, as well as, outline for biological recultivation of those soils. Regarding this, the table of indicator plants appropriate for the bioecological properties is developed. As it is known, ecological scale or degree, abundance (in points), stages, that's, the height of plants (cm), and draft cover are mentioned in the table.

According to the results of scientific and research works conducted, “indication map” of indicator plants in the soils contaminated with oil and oil products creates a basis for the implementation of environmental protection measures with scientific and practical basis after the compilation of soil recultivation project and specification of phytosociological maps in researches by the surface and aerospace methods.

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